

Automated Pop-to-A Cappella Score Generation

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Abstract

A significant number of research has explored the co-creation and automated generation of symbolic music across various genres. In this work, we investigate the potential for a comprehensive, automated system that transforms polyphonic pop music into six-part a cappella sheet music, featuring a lead vocal line, SATB harmonies, and vocal percussion. Leveraging advanced AI techniques—including pre-trained models and custom algorithms—the system is designed to tackle challenges in music transcription, feature extraction, and SATB harmonization. Our approach centers on curating paired datasets that align solo piano MIDI scores with corresponding SATB a cappella arrangements, forming the basis for a deep learning system that generates SATB choruses. A subsequent rule-based module then creates a suitable vocal percussion part to complement the music. Overall, this prototype bridges the gap between traditional manual transcription methods and modern AI-driven music processing, paving the way towards automated creation of accessible, high-quality a cappella arrangements.

1 Introduction

A cappella vocal covers of pop music enjoy growing popularity for their expressive appeal and adaptability. Creating accurate and stylistically faithful arrangements, however, remains a labor-intensive task: traditional workflows rely on expert musicians to manually dissect complex polyphonic recordings into multiple vocal lines, making high-quality score production both time consuming and inaccessible to amateur musicians or general music enthusiasts. Recent advances in AI-based music transcription and generative modeling promise to automate this process, lowering the expertise barrier to promote the art of a cappella music to the less-capable audience, and to inspire music education, performance preparation, and creative composition. We acknowledge that much of the creative reward in a cappella arranging comes from hands-on craftsmanship itself; we aim to assist and streamline routine tasks, not to replace the artistic decisions that make each arrangement unique.

To this end, we propose a web-based system that converts raw recording of pop music into six-part a cappella sheet music—comprising a lead vocal melody, SATB harmonies, and a vocal percussion track—while preserving stylistic fidelity and adhering to human vocal ranges. By integrating pre-trained audio-to-MIDI transcription, a deep-learning harmonization module with musical constraint penalties, and a rule-based vocal percussion module within an intuitive interface, our system aims to offer an innovative approach for reducing the creative threshold towards professional-grade a cappella arrangement for educators, performers, and composers.

It is worth noting that this work presents a prototype experiment aiming at the exploration of new possibilities in the field of a cappella music score creation. While the system is still in its early stages and far from perfect, it addresses a relatively rare topic in academic research, where few studies have focused on tools to assist beginner singers and educators, who may lack accessible resources in this domain. Importantly, this system is not intended to replace artists or composers, but rather to serve as

a supportive tool that lightens the workload of musicians, thereby encouraging further revision with a focus on creativity and originality.

Some demo of the system can be found at <https://bit.ly/aimc-acappella>, which includes the generated parts of one test song and a human-arranged version for comparison.

2 Background

Previous studies on related topics have informed our work regarding system design and considerations. DeepChoir (Wu et al., 2023), a Bi-LSTM-based model, focuses on generating four-part chorales from solely the melody lines based on classical music datasets with controllable harmonic, yet neglects the dynamic and diverse characteristics of instrumental parts in a pop context. DJ-Agent (Jiang, 2023) is likely the most similar project which applies deep reinforcement learning guided by explicit classical music theory to produce a cappella accompaniments. Yet, the work also employs traditional Bach chorale datasets and neglects stylized rhythm, harmonies and vocal percussion elements which highlight the significance of a cappella music. From these studies, we identify the over-reliance on classical or curated datasets that overlook modern a cappella styles, and a lack of focus on an all-in-one a cappella production system to ease the creative process for novices.

Our work aims to fill the gaps by developing a comprehensive system that emphasizes accessibility and practical utility rather than solely stylistic generation. This distinct focus and approach demonstrate the originality and relevance of our contribution.

To stand out from previous studies, our automation of transforming pop recordings into a cappella scores aims to address three key challenges. First, publicly available paired datasets of pop audio and corresponding multi-voice a cappella arrangements are scarce, forcing reliance on weakly aligned or transfer-learned resources and limiting the expressive range of supervised models. Second, polyphonic pop audio exhibits overlapping instruments and vocals, making reliable melody and harmony extraction difficult without advanced transcription models. Third, pop a cappella arrangements demand dynamic harmonies, syncopated rhythms, and vocal percussion—features that differ markedly from classical choral conventions and require flexible generation methods.

These issues can potentially be tackled individually, supported by recent works in the source separation module and audio-to-MIDI transcription. For example, the *Spleeter* Python library by Deezer (Hennequin et al., 2020) uses a U-Net neural network to efficiently separate vocals and accompaniment from mixed audio by processing spectrograms and reconstructing isolated tracks. Projects like *Pop2Piano* (Choi and Lee, 2023), *PiCoGen2* (Tan et al., 2024) and *Music2Midi* (Yip and Chau, 2025) employ transformer-based architectures trained on large, weakly aligned corpora, overcoming alignment issues and improving musical coherence to offer high-fidelity feature extraction in MusicXML or MIDI formats.

For harmonization, measure-aligned sequence-to-sequence models augmented with musical constraint penalties ensure generated SATB parts to respect vocal range and chordal completeness. Complementary rule-based engines, informed by beatboxing practices and onset-density heuristics, produce stylized vocal percussion patterns in 16th-note resolution.

Together, these advances form the foundation of our end-to-end a cappella arrangement pipeline.

3 Methodology

Our system implements a fully automated pipeline that transforms a raw pop-music audio file into a complete six-part a cappella score—comprising a single-line vocal melody, four-part SATB harmonies, and a vocal percussion track—delivered through a web-based interface. These three modules were chosen because preserving the original vocal melody maintains the song’s identity and reduces transcription complexity. Note that later in our output, the four-part SATB harmonies should deliver time-tested choral textures and harmonic depth, and a dedicated vocal percussion track should provide rhythmic drive and emulate percussive elements within an a cappella context. The overall architecture (see Figure 1) consists of five key stages: audio-to-piano transcription, melody extraction and preprocessing, SATB harmonization (with its supporting dataset), vocal percussion generation, and user-interface presentation.

Figure 1: Overall system architecture in modular component structure.

We selected the *PiCoGen2* Transformer for audio-to-MIDI conversion due to its proven accuracy on full-mix pop recordings, offering robust extraction of both melody and harmony information directly from the complete song. This approach streamlines transcription by avoiding multiple separation steps and ensures a high-fidelity piano cover that provides a solid foundation for all downstream processing.

For SATB harmonization, we employ four independent Bi-LSTM encoder–decoder networks, which naturally incorporate our range and consonance penalties at the measure level, delivering realistic choral textures without excessive model complexity. And for vocal percussion, a rule-based onset-density engine paired with a Kick/Snare/Hi-hat template library produces consistent, human-like rhythm patterns without requiring large, specialized beatbox datasets.

3.1 Audio-to-piano transcription

We convert uploaded MP3/WAV files into a unified piano transcription (MusicXML or MIDI) using the *PiCoGen2* transformer (Tan et al., 2024). First, the raw audio is transformed into log-mel spectrogram frames and passed through *PiCoGen2*’s pretrained audio encoder. The decoder then autoregressively generates a stream of MIDI tokens—each encoding pitch, onset, and duration—for every note in the mix. A lightweight post-processing step assembles these tokens into a MusicXML score, preserving the full polyphonic texture as a single piano cover. This one-step transcription captures all melodic and harmonic content needed for downstream melody extraction and arrangement.

We adopt this unified piano-MIDI representation to abstract away original instrumentation—so that both SATB harmonization and vocal percussion modules operate on consistent harmonic and rhythmic information—thereby simplifying model design and improving cross-song robustness.

3.2 Melody extraction and preprocessing

Once the full piano cover is generated, we apply a custom Python post-processing pipeline to separate the lead melody from its accompaniment. For each measure, the script computes note density—counting unique onsets—and ranks pitches by their spectral prominence to identify the most salient notes. It then applies voice-leading heuristics, favoring minimal melodic leaps and sustained tones, to distill these candidates into a coherent, single-line melody. All remaining notes are retained as the accompaniment, preserving the original harmonic progressions and rhythmic patterns.

Our initial attempt was to isolate the vocal track using the *Spleeter* library before feeding it into *PiCoGen2*, but we found that the resulting MIDI suffered from residual accompaniment artifacts and

timing drift. By extracting the melody directly from our unified piano-MIDI cover, we obtain cleaner, perfectly measure-aligned melodies and more reliable extraction overall.

It is noted that due to the selection of the highest-prominence note per measure, the resulting melody may exhibit unnatural behavior, such as abrupt drops and jumps, overly sustained tones without rests, and occasional mis-separation of the vocal line (as seen in one of the test song “Dynamite”). These errors could be acceptable since the vocal melody part primarily serves as a reference for users to identify corresponding sections in the original pop song. In practical a cappella performances, vocalists often introduce their own interpretative variations, such as subtle changes in pitch or rhythm. Users are not expected to replicate the melody exactly. Further human adjustments and artistic liberties are expected.

This decoupling yields a clean monophonic melody track for the vocal line and a rich polyphonic accompaniment track for downstream SATB harmonization and vocal percussion modules.

3.3 SATB harmonization

3.3.1 Dataset construction

To train our SATB harmonization models, we assemble a custom paired dataset of 20 pop song piano covers and their corresponding SATB a cappella arrangements, all sourced from *Musescore*¹ under non-commercial academic terms. Each piano–a cappella pair is parsed into measure-level token sequences of the form `{pitch}_{offset}_{duration}`, a design choice made to balance sequence length and musical coherence: measures naturally align with harmonic changes and reduce token-sequence explosion (from thousands of 16th-note steps to a few hundred measures per song). These sequences are then aligned using a semi-automated pipeline: we first compute a Jaccard similarity matrix over sets of (pitch, onset) tuples to flag high-correspondence measures, and subsequently perform manual measure-to-measure adjustments—composing missing passages when necessary, synchronizing key and tempo metadata, and pruning extraneous parts—via MuseScore and the *music21* library (Cuthbert and Ariza, 2010). To increase model robustness and mitigate overfitting, we generate five transposed variants of each base song by shifting pitches randomly within $\pm 1-2$ semitones.

The final training set thus comprises roughly 10,000 measure-aligned token pairs per voice, providing a rich foundation for learning stylistically faithful SATB harmonization (see Table 1).

Table 1: Overview of the piano-a cappella paired dataset

Metric	Value
Songs Genre	Pop Songs
Base songs	20
Number of measures per song	20–200
Augmented measures	9721
Token format	<code>{pitch}_{offset}_{duration}</code>

3.3.2 Model architecture and training

We train four separate Bi-LSTM encoder–decoder networks, one for each of the Soprano, Alto, Tenor, and Bass voices, processing the music one measure at a time and decoding each output sequence greedily. Within each model, the encoder is a bidirectional LSTM that reads the tokenized input for a single measure and captures musical context from both past and future positions. To initialize the decoder, we fuse the encoder’s state by summing its final hidden and cell states from the forward and backward passes into a single context vector. The unidirectional LSTM decoder then uses this combined state to autoregressively generate the sequence of pitch–offset–duration tokens for its assigned voice, producing one token at a time until the measure is complete (see Figure 2).

¹<https://musescore.com>

Figure 2: Architecture of the proposed bidirectional-encoder / unidirectional-decoder LSTM model for SATB harmonization.

Loss function. A composite loss balances token cross-entropy with auxiliary musical penalties:

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{CE}} + \lambda \mathcal{L}_{\text{aux}}, \quad \mathcal{L}_{\text{aux}} = \alpha \mathcal{L}_{\text{range}} + \beta \mathcal{L}_{\text{harmony}}. \quad (1)$$

The hyperparameters were chosen via empirical tuning on a small held-out validation set, where the interpolation ratio ($\alpha : \beta = 1.2 : 0.8$) was found to emphasize range adherence slightly more than harmonic regularization, and $\lambda = 0.12$ was found to produce a balanced trade-off between token prediction accuracy and musicality. In Equation 1, we thus set $\lambda = 0.12$, $\alpha = 1.2$, and $\beta = 0.8$. Here, \mathcal{L}_{aux} comprises a voice-range penalty (notes outside empirically defined MIDI ranges for each voice) and a chord-harmony penalty (lack of consonant intervals). Vocal-range bounds follow common practice (i.e., Soprano: MIDI 60–79, Alto: MIDI 55–74, Tenor: MIDI 48–67, Bass: MIDI 40–60). The hyperparameter λ controls the trade-off between the standard cross-entropy loss and our musicality penalties, while within $\mathcal{L}_{\text{aux}} = \alpha \mathcal{L}_{\text{range}} + \beta \mathcal{L}_{\text{harmony}}$, α sets how strongly out-of-range notes are penalized and β sets how strongly disharmonic intervals are penalized.

Training regimen. Each voice model is trained independently on GPU-accelerated hardware. We monitor three primary metrics—cross-entropy loss, auxiliary penalty loss, and perplexity—across epochs. All four models exhibit steady convergence, with near-zero final losses and token-level accuracy approaching 99%, confirming the efficacy of our penalized training strategy.

3.4 Vocal percussion module

In our vocal percussion module, we begin by analyzing the instrumental transcription’s rhythmic profile at a global level—calculating the average onset density, determining the key mode (major or minor), and measuring the overall tempo—to classify the song’s “strength” as light, medium, or strong. We then divide the track into consecutive four-measure blocks, compute each block’s average onset count relative to the global density, and merge adjacent blocks with identical labels into segments of up to eight measures. For each segment, we randomly select a 16-step kick/snare pattern from a curated Pattern Bank that matches its strength classification, insert a number of hi-hat hits (“T”) proportional to the segment’s onset density, and apply this finalized pattern uniformly across all measures in the segment. The sequence of beatbox symbols—“B” for kick, “K” for snare, and “T” for hi-hat—is then mapped to MIDI events using a woodblock timbre and annotated with the corresponding syllables as MusicXML lyrics, ensuring both audio playback and visual clarity. To

handle pre-measure pick-ups, we detect any initial non-zero onsets and insert aligned rests at the start of the percussion track so that measure counts remain consistent across parts.

3.5 User interface

Our user interface is implemented as a Flask-based web application that guides users through each stage of the a cappella generation pipeline without requiring any local Python installation. After selecting and uploading an MP3 or WAV file—complete with an animated progress indicator—users can navigate through dedicated tabs to invoke piano transcription, melody extraction, SATB harmonization, and vocal percussion generation in sequence. Once processing is complete, each part’s MusicXML score is rendered directly in the browser alongside embedded audio playback controls that allow solo or combined listening. Finally, users can export either individual voice parts or the full six-part arrangement in MusicXML or MIDI format for use in external notation software. The asynchronous backend tasks ensure responsive interaction, and built-in error handling notifies users of unsupported formats or runtime issues, making the entire system easily deployable on intranet or cloud platforms.

4 Experiment and evaluation

We conduct a comprehensive evaluation of our end-to-end system for automated pop-to-a cappella score generation, focusing on three main aspects: model output quality, musicality, and system performance.

4.1 Model output evaluation

For the test set selection, three diverse pop songs: “Before You Go” (Lewis Capaldi, 2020), “Counting Stars” (OneRepublic, 2013), and “Dynamite” (HYBE LABELS, 2020), are selected to assess generalization across different time signatures, key signatures, and harmonic structures (see Table 2). None were used in training or data augmentation, ensuring a fair test of model robustness.

Table 2: General musical information of the three test songs in our system evaluation

Song	Time signature	Key signature	Tempo	Rhythm consistency	Harmonic structure
Before You Go	6/8	E♭ major	112 bpm	Varies	Weaker
Counting Stars	4/4	C♯ minor	122 bpm	Consistent	Stronger
Dynamite	4/4	E major	114 bpm	Partly consistent	Weaker

We automatically assess the generated SATB harmonizations using the following metrics, reflecting both music theory and practical pop a cappella conventions:

- Chord Accuracy: % of measures forming valid triads ($\geq 90\%$)
- Voice Range Violation: % of notes outside standard SATB ranges ($\leq 35\%$)
- Structural Repetition: % of measures repeated identically across voices ($\leq 10\%$)

Note that the thresholds are based on empirical expectations in SATB-style harmony and human composition patterns in pop a cappella. They are defined based on music theory conventions, human compositional practices, and observed characteristics of real-world a cappella arrangements.

Chord Accuracy: A valid triadic harmony is a fundamental requirement in SATB-style composition. Since most Western pop harmonies are built on major/minor triads, we set our chord-accuracy threshold at 90%, which exceeds the 75–87% weighted chord-symbol recall achieved by state-of-the-art automatic chord estimation systems (Odekerken et al., 2021). This threshold ensures musical credibility and harmonic completeness while allowing minor stylistic or rhythmic simplifications.

Voice Range Violation: Given the pop music context, a more lenient range is accepted compared to traditional choral music. Contemporary a cappella often stretches vocal limits for expressive or

stylistic purposes. Due to the lack of publicly available statistical data on vocal range usage in pop a cappella, we temporarily set our violation threshold at 35% as a reasonable upper limit to highlight extreme cases, and plan to perform more rigorous empirical validation in future work.

Structural Repetition: Repetition can give a song cohesion, but too much risks monotony or stifled development. We therefore monitor repeated measure-level and phrase-level patterns during generation and encourage variation—melodic, harmonic, or rhythmic—to keep each section dynamic.

Take our test song “Dynamite” as a result evaluation example. This harmonization achieves 98.5% chord accuracy, a 31.6% voice-range violation rate, and only 1.1% structural repetition. Other test songs show similar results, which are well within our defined thresholds, demonstrating both harmonic correctness and adherence to vocal constraints, though further refinement in voice allocation could improve alignment with vocal ergonomics.

4.2 Output musicality evaluation

To assess musical expressiveness and realism, we conducted a blind listening test inspired by the Turing’s Test. Each test set includes three versions of a pop song: the original song, a human-arranged a cappella, and an AI-generated a cappella arrangement from our system (order randomized). Volunteer subjects were asked to identify the AI-generated version, with an identification failure to obtain a test pass. Subjects also rate the vocal percussion quality using a 1–10 scale. The blind listening test was conducted using the same test set of three diverse pop songs as in Table 2: “Before You Go”, “Counting Stars”, and “Dynamite”, with each participant completing the listening test separately for all three songs.

The total of 13 subjects were local university students of various musical backgrounds (musicians and non-musicians), mimicking a general teenage audience of pop music. Although the listening tracks were rendered with instrumental sounds rather than a cappella voices, all subjects were clearly briefed on the project’s objectives and evaluation methodologies to ensure clarity and avoid confusion during the assessment.

In blind-listening tests across three songs, subjects correctly identified the AI-generated versions in only 6 of 39 trials (3 songs \times 13 subjects), 4 from our best-performing test song “Counting Stars” and 2 from “Dynamite”. Subjects then rated vocal percussion quality at 8.2 for the song “Before You Go”, 9.6 for “Counting Stars”, and 8.9 for “Dynamite” out of 10, underscoring the musical plausibility of our rule-based designs. Though some outputs were described as “slightly mechanical” or lacking in motif development, suggesting areas for future improvement.

5 Conclusion

We have developed a fully automated web application that converts pop audio into six-part a cappella scores—combining a unified piano transcription, custom melody extraction, four Bi-LSTM SATB harmonizers, and a rule-based vocal percussion module—delivered via an intuitive Flask interface. Our prototype reliably produces musically coherent harmonies within human vocal ranges and rhythmically consistent percussion, with synchronized MusicXML previews and exportable MIDI outputs.

Despite achieving musically coherent results and demonstrating the feasibility of automated a cappella arrangement generation, the current system has several limitations. First, the SATB harmonization model, while effective in many contexts, struggles with complex rhythmic patterns such as syncopation or less common time signatures that are sparsely represented in the corpus (e.g., 6/8). This reflects a constraint of the measure-level tokenization and the lack of attention mechanisms in the LSTM-based model, which limits the system’s ability to model long-range musical dependencies and global phrasing structures.

Second, we also note that by decoding each measure entirely independently, our current system might produce shifting voice assignments at measure boundaries, potentially increasing singer complexity. In future work, it is possible to add a cross-measure smoothing or voice-tracking mechanism to maintain assignment coherence and further reduce singers’ burden.

Moreover, the vocal percussion module relies on a rule-based engine grounded in beatboxing conventions, which, although interpretable and efficient, lacks dynamic variation and expressive nuance

beyond the three core syllables (B, K, T). As such, it cannot replicate complex percussive articulations such as rolls, open hi-hats, or ghost notes. Moreover, the fixed rhythmic templates may limit stylistic adaptability to genres outside mainstream pop.

Future work will focus on incorporating attention-based harmonization models that attend over multi-measure contexts to handle complex rhythms, expand percussion expressivity, and add real-time score editing. These enhancements will further democratize high-quality a cappella arrangement for educators, performers, and creators.

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